

OBJECTS IN PURGATORY: HOW WE LIVE WITH UNCHERISHED GIFTS.

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ABSTRACT

The Campaign for Objects in Purgatory is a creative research project that investigates user-product attachment by exploring the emotional conflicts embodied in uncherished gifts. By seeking to find out why uncherished gifts are kept, and where in the home they are located, the project draws attention to social and domestic rituals that shape emotional attachment.

This paper reviews the Objects in Purgatory 'live exhibition' as a qualitative research method, and as a means of engaging an audience in collective reflection on gift giving and accumulation. It also examines the data collected through the exhibition against research from anthropology, psychology and design. The findings suggest that we can dislike an object and yet still keep and value it. This challenges notions of emotional attachment by suggesting that an emotional bond need not be based on desire. Can we design products whose value is shaped through diverse social and domestic rituals?

Keywords: Emotion, attachment, possessions, identity, value

INTRODUCTION

The term 'throw-away society' has been in popular use for more than fifty years, and is accompanied by an understanding that we carelessly create waste by discarding functional products we no longer desire. Research in design (Chapman 2005, Schifferstein & Zwartkuis-Pelgrim 2008) considers emotional attachment in human-product relationships as a means of prolonging product lifespan, and therefore reducing the high turnover of consumer goods.

Theories of emotional attachment and their application to design are often discussed in terms of encouraging the development of a strong emotional person-product bond (Odom et al 2009, Russo et al 2011). This paper seeks to explore some of the more subjective and elusive factors affecting how we decide whether we should keep an object. To do this it focuses attention on the development of emotional attachment through domestic and social ritual, in negotiation with people and space.

The discussions here centre on the Campaign for Objects in Purgatory, a creative research project that investigates the notion of the uncherished gift and seeks to reveal how and where people keep them. Uncherished gifts that are nevertheless kept offer rich potential for exploration, as they usually embody a contradiction in emotional value. As much as the recipient might want to rid themselves of a gifted object, they may also desire to keep it.

The first manifestation of the project was a 'live exhibition' that displayed a growing collection of Objects in Purgatory contributed by visitors. The aim of this paper is to review the Objects in Purgatory live exhibition as a qualitative research method, and to identify possible veins for further exploration. It is seen as an early stage on a long term body of research on emotional sustainability.

Related projects (from a range of disciplines) place emphasis on cherished objects that endure over a lifetime, and rarely reveal the fluid and negotiated nature of attachment to most possessions. Campaign for Objects in Purgatory uncovers the challenges uncherished gifts present to an individual's sense of

identity and reveals the contradictory emotions that these troublesome possessions mediate. The object's location in the home is discussed as this helps bring to light the strategies employed to prevent regular confrontations with the emotions it embodies.

This paper explores the above as follows: through a review of the Objects in Purgatory exhibition as a method; qualitative and quantitative analysis of the submissions; expansion of some of the core findings against a literature review of research from anthropology, psychology and design; and implications for design.

METHOD (LIVE EXHIBITION)

RELATED WORK

Recent projects from a range of disciplines (art and design, academic research and journalism) have actively engaged the public in recording and exploring meaningful personal narratives attached to objects. These include 'A Shoebox of Snow' (BBC Radio 4), the 'Totem' project (a collaboration between 5 universities), and 'Things' (artist Keith Wilson and the Wellcome Collection). Anthropological studies of the material culture of the home (Attfield 2000, Miller 2008 and 2001, Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton 1981, McCracken, 2005) address everyday cohabitation with possessions. However, the above projects and studies place emphasis on the consideration of objects as mediators of memory and conveyors of meaning, and tend to give precedence to possessions that are kept and valued. There is a lack of literature investigating objects whose value and meaning is less secure; objects on a more precarious journey between acquisition and dispossession.

LIVE EXHIBITION

The Objects in Purgatory live exhibition relied entirely on audience submissions for its exhibits. Visitors to the exhibition were invited to contribute their uncherished gifts by submitting an object, photo, sketch, written submission or recorded audio narrative. The exhibition grew as these were received, and a rich sense of collective ownership developed. The dynamic format of the exhibition simultaneously provided a creative means of

collecting data, and a successful method of encouraging audience engagement.

The exhibition took place in the Sheffield Institute of Arts Gallery over 8 days in May 2011. It was attended by members of the public, but the majority of participants were university community.

Processes of audience engagement

The exhibition was advertised prior to its launch through local press, radio, posters, flyers and internal emails. The invitation to submit an object was a straightforward and open process encouraging participation. At the exhibition visitors encountered the exhibition posters,¹ the exhibits, and then an exhibition assistant who provided a short verbal explanation of the project aims and attempted to engage the visitor in a semi-structured dialogue.² Visitors were offered a choice of methods of recording the object and its story. This open process encouraged participants to talk about their objects as they recalled them, and helped develop trust and engagement.

As the exhibition evolved and its visual impact increased, it developed an identity and agency of its own that propelled data collection. Visitors were inspired and provoked by the existing submissions to recall and vocalise their experiences. Enjoyment of the act of contributing came through in the consideration and care given to quality of drawing, layout and in some entertaining and humorous narratives.

Uncherished gifts aren't usually publically discussed, as gift giving is subject to widely understood implicit rules of obligation. Participating in the Objects in Purgatory exhibition is a public act of disclosure that gives people permission to unburden themselves of uncomfortable feelings, and connect to others through a universal experience.

¹ The text on the exhibition aid read as follows: 'Have you ever received a gift that you don't like but feel you should keep? How do you decide where to keep it, and for how long? Bring a photo, make a sketch or tell the story of your uncherished gift, then take your free brooch and wear with joy! Contributions remain anonymous.'

² This included requesting information on the object's location in the home, and participants were encouraged to talk about why the object is in purgatory.

Effectiveness of submission methods

A total of 72 objects were submitted through the exhibition process. The breakdown of this is as follows: 57 annotated drawings, 12 physical objects, 4 photographs of the object in-situ, 25 recorded audio narratives, and 1 written narrative. 21 submissions consisted of more than one type of media.

Annotated drawings form the majority of submissions and were key to the effectiveness of the exhibition, as they allowed visitors to make immediate responses and for a quantity of submissions to build up. Drawing and writing facilitate personal expression, but objective information about the object and its location is limited. [see figure 1] Photographs contain more objective information on location but they were not a popular method of submission, possibly because they require activity beyond the exhibition. Recorded audio narratives allow more detail about the object and its story to be recorded. It is possible to identify expression of emotion in many audio recordings as well as in drawn and written submissions. (See Findings.) Physical objects provided focal points for discussions about their context [figure 2].

Limitations

Audience engagement processes were kept open in order to encourage participation. As a result, there are limitations to the depth of data gathered from submissions. For example, no official data was collected on age. For this reason it's not always possible to make exhaustive quantitative readings, but it is possible to identify patterns and focal points for future research and restaging of the exhibition.

It should be noted that a project of this kind cannot achieve the richness of a large-scale anthropological research investigation. However, a small number of submissions provide a greater depth of insight, and the submission process elicited rich seams of unrecorded dialogue that indicate potential for collecting a greater depth of data. This could lead into further, more in depth studies in the future, using established home interview techniques as well as creative development of the live exhibition, perhaps by developing the role of collective disclosure.

Figure 1. Annotated drawing: Shawl with beads, modified by recipient and kept on display.

Figure 2. Discussion between participant and exhibition assistant of an object as it is submitted to the exhibition.

The process of participation is voluntary and it is possible that some participants were reserved in divulging memories and experiences, out of concern for hurting loved ones or exposing their own feelings. Consequently there may be a lack of objects that evoke deep emotional responses, however the

findings show that the submitted objects are nevertheless extremely worthy of study.

Social agency

The live exhibition as method has value as a means of gathering data, but also of creating dialogue beyond the research community. The exhibition stimulated dialogue beyond the process of participation and provoked some visitors to re-evaluate either their objects (some were re-embraced, and some were divested), or their attitudes to gift giving and accumulation. The exhibition has social agency; it is a catalyst for reflection on gift giving and accumulation.

Data analysis

The method for data analysis builds on Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton's (1981) two stage method of categorizing firstly the objects studied, and secondly the meaning of the object to the respondent. The first stage was to categorise the more straightforward descriptive data as follows: objects;³ the relationship of giver to recipient; and the location of the object in the home.

The second stage sought to interpret and categorise expressions of value connected to the objects. This builds on Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton's 'meaning' categorisation but in this case meaning is broken down into 'Reasons cited for devaluing an object' and 'Reasons cited for valuing an object'. This allows for discussions to encompass the possibility of a conflict in the object's value to the respondent. This stage was then extended to identify emotions embodied in the object and illicit by the submission process.

FINDINGS

The findings have been structured as follows: Givers; Objects submitted; Location of object in home; Conflicts in value; and Emotions expressed and recorded through submissions.

³ Some of C&R's object categories have been reconstituted to make distinctions relevant to this project, for example making decorative / functional distinctions to the 'sculpture' category by separating surface-standing ornamental objects, and vases and candlesticks.

GIVERS

Over half of the submissions (42 of 72) concerned gifts that were from family members (see table 1), and the majority of these (33) were given by a member of an older generation (see table 2). Other submissions are from friends, family friends and colleagues, and there is a notable group of objects that have either been found, made or bought by self.

From family members (including spouses and extended family)*	42
From friends or groups of friends*	11
From professional relationships	3
Bought, found or collected by self	8
Unknown	9

Table 1. Relationship of giver to recipient. *Includes one submission of a group of objects given by both friends and family

Givers of an older generation to recipient	
Grandparents:	9
Parents:	12
Parents in law:	4
Aunts and Uncles:	8
Total:	33
Givers of same generation as recipient	
Siblings:	4
Spouse:	1
Total:	5
Givers of a younger generation to recipient	
Children:	1
Nieces and nephews:	1
Total:	2

TABLE 2. Givers in the family: relationship of giver to recipient (n.b. 2 givers cited are relatives but the relationship to giver isn't specified)

OBJECTS SUBMITTED

There isn't capacity within this paper to discuss the large diversity of types of object submitted (see table 3), and all possible implications. Perhaps the single connecting factor between most of the objects (68 of

72) is their small scale. They are small enough to be carried but are usually designed to sit on a surface.⁴

Sculpture: Surface-standing ornamental objects	15
Vases and candlesticks	3
Clothes, shoes, bags	14
Kitchen and tableware	8
Toys	6
Books, magazines and printed ephemera	6
jewellery	5
Timepieces	4
Wall mounted decorative objects / visual art	4
Audio / visual media	2
Tools	1
Cosmetics	1
Furniture	1
Miscellaneous	3

TABLE 3: Objects submitted (n.b. 5 submissions included more than one type of object)

Figure 3. Photograph of object in situ and recorded audio narrative: Carriage clock, kept on an Ikea bookshelf in study / office area.

Location of object in home:

There is a tendency for Objects in Purgatory to be kept where they are relatively accessible but not visible in daily life. Of the 72 submissions, 60 cite a location, usually a room or an item of furniture. 11 submissions identify rooms and spaces peripheral to the main living rooms (see table 4), such as

workspaces and sheds, including 3 references to the bedroom in the home of the participant's parents.⁵ These spaces are a step away from the main living rooms and provide opportunities for keeping an object whilst not encountering it regularly.

Specific locations within rooms usually refer to storage furniture (See table 5: 28 references) but a smaller number (10) are stored in locations where they are visible in daily life, such as on a mantelpiece. In more detailed submissions it is interesting to note that participants have strategies for limiting the prominence of objects kept in visible locations. For example, the clock in figure 3 is kept in a visible location on a bookcase in the office area, where it is not always noticed because attention is focused on the computer.

There is also a tendency to keep functional Objects in Purgatory in the place commonly designated for them. For example, a hair clip kept at the bottom of a bathroom box, or a wedding crockery set kept unused in the kitchen cupboard. This appears on the surface to 'disguise' the objects as used and valued possessions, implying an obligation not only to keep a gift but also to fulfill its use potential.

Bedroom:	8
Attic / loft:	5
Kitchen:	5
Bathroom:	1
Hall:	1
Rooms and spaces peripheral to main living spaces:	11
(Workshop, study / office, parental home, studio / office, converted garage, garage, room next to garage, shed)	

TABLE 4. Rooms cited

⁴ Only 2 objects submitted are cited as devalued due to their large size, and 2 items of furniture have been submitted.

⁵ Several of the participants in the exhibition were students, and this reflects their particular transitional phase of life.

Bookcase / shelf:	8	10	Objects visible in daily life
Mantelpiece:	2		
Cupboard:	11	28	Objects invisible in daily life
Wardrobe:	7		
Drawer:	5		
In a box:	5		

TABLE 5. Items of furniture cited more than once. Also mentioned: in wallet, on dressing table, worn on finger, behind curtain, behind television, behind photo

Where items of furniture are cited, the objects' locations are often described in relation to them e.g. 'bottom of', 'behind', 'on top of'. This suggests mini-periphery zones within and around items of furniture that can be appropriated for storage of objects that there is no desire to see or use regularly, but for which deep storage⁶ is inappropriate.

Whilst most descriptions of objects and locations are very minimal, a small number of participants use more descriptive terms to communicate the relationship of the object to its location, such as 'buried away', or 'stuffed right at back'. (See table 6) This language seems to imply either an ambivalence towards the object, or a desire to make it difficult to encounter.

'buried' in cupboard / 'buried away' in garage
'sits' on dressing table / 'sits untouched' in cupboard
on a 'dusty' shelf
'straight into' attic
'closed box' in attic
'stuffed into' cupboards and drawers / 'stuffed right at back' of desk
'hidden' behind wardrobe
'lanushed' in my bottom drawer for years

Table 6. Descriptive language used to describe relationship of object to location

CONFLICTS IN VALUE

An Object in Purgatory embodies a conflict between its uncherished status and other values which prevent the recipient from ridding themselves of the object. The diversity of conflicts evident in the submissions is

extensive, as a different mix of factors impacts on each object. For this reason the two sides of the conflict are examined independently, as 'Reasons cited for devaluing an object' and 'Reasons cited for valuing an object'. There are then two examples outlining conflicts in value.

Figure 4. Annotated drawing: Jewellery box, kept on a dusty shelf.

Reasons cited for devaluing an object

In most submissions (63 of 72) participants cite a reason for devaluing the object. These vary in detail, but several (26) can clearly be identified as explicit expressions of distaste or dislike (rather than, say, functional failure) [see figures 1 and 4]. These often relate to differences in taste and style, particularly across generations [see figure 7], and are frequently conveyed alongside the recipient's disappointment or incomprehension at what they see as a misrepresentation of their identity. Where more detail is provided, distaste is often expressed alongside disappointment with a fake brand, perceived material cheapness [figure 4], or with a style conflicting that of the home interior.

Several submissions (16) cite reasons of unfulfilled usefulness or functionality for devaluing an object, for example if the object is of no practical use to the recipient [figure 5], broken, or if there are simply too many of the same object in their possession.

⁶ see Odom (2010)

Figure 5. Annotated drawing: Walking stick (no location given).

In a minority of cases (5) an object's status is compromised because it is valued differently by people living together in one space. For example, in figure 6 the object is valued by the participant but not her spouse, and in two other submissions the participant doesn't like the object but is impelled to keep it because it is valued by a child.

Other reasons for not valuing an object cited more than once include objects representing the wrong brand or team, or the worn and aged appearance of object.

Reasons cited for valuing an object

Two thirds of participants (45) have indicated a reason for valuing the object whereas others appear to have kept their objects out of a straightforward sense of obligation.⁷

⁷ This sense of obligation is difficult to unpick as most submissions are spontaneous rather than reflective and detailed. It raises complex questions about exchange rituals that will be touched on in the literature review, but that ultimately are beyond the scope of this paper.

Figure 6. Written narrative and physical object: Easter Island ornamental figure, kept hidden behind photo on sideboard.

There are a significant number of submissions (15) where the object is valued because it embodies a valued relationship with another person. At times affection for the giver is expressed explicitly through the narrative [figure 7], but a valued connection to the giver is also demonstrated in other ways. The object can evoke a memory of an important person (in some cases deceased), or pleasant memories of receiving the gift. An object that is inherited or passed down (8) can embody significant memories and relationships, and can be valued simply because it was cherished or lived with by a previous generation(s).⁸

⁸ However, these routes of acquisition don't always imply unequivocal value and can create problematic possessions.

Figure 7. Annotated drawing: Watch, kept in bottom cupboard.

In 3 submissions value has developed as a result of a shared private ritual: gifts exchanged between giver and recipient regularly or repeatedly that become the subject of a long-term shared joke, and may also serve to nurture the interpersonal relationship. In addition to more intimate rituals established between giver and recipient, value is (perhaps predictably) created by significant social and family rituals (6), encompassing graduation from university, marriages, and gestures of welcome to the family.

Value created through some kind of personal investment is evident in 13 submissions.⁹ This includes making the object personally (usually the giver), or significantly modifying it (the recipient). In several cases the recipient has found the object themselves, and has felt impelled by the object on that first encounter to keep it. In others, value is expressed as an appreciation of the effort that has been made by the giver, for example, personally transporting a fragile object over a long distance, or (a

child) saving up pocket money over a long period of time.

Some recipients clearly like the objects and a small number of objects (4) reflect an aspect of an individual's sense of identity or professional interests.

Examples outlining conflicts in value:

The diversity of conflicts in value expressed in the submissions mean it is not possible to identify significant patterns between reasons for valuing and reasons for devaluing. However 13 of the submissions containing explicit expressions of distaste or dislike gave a clear reason for valuing the object, demonstrating that an object that isn't liked can still evoke a strong emotional bond.

The following two examples outline conflicts in the personal value of an object. The first is a drawn and annotated submission, and the second is a photograph and more detailed audio narrative.

The submission in Figure 7 describes the gift of a watch from the recipient's grandfather. The recipient clearly doesn't like the watch ('it's mingin') but keeps it out of affection for the giver ('he's a legend so could never throw it away'). There is also evidence of difference in taste and style across generations, as the watch was 'cool' when Grandad was his age.

More reflective submissions contain a greater depth of information and demonstrate some of the detail of how an object's value develops. For example, the carriage clock in figure 3 (mentioned above) has undergone subtle transformations in value. The participant believes it to be of little material value and probably acquired by the giver as a free gift. The clock was initially kept simply because it was felt appropriate to do so in acceptance of the gift. It was brought to the attention of the recipients every now and again as it was the subject of a commonplace ritual; changing the batteries. However it was eventually superseded in its function by a nearby computer and the batteries were no longer changed. Following the death of the giver the bond between person and object strengthened, and it became harder to contemplate getting rid of it. Ultimately its status has been elevated and its location referred to as 'a bit

⁹ Several objects are valued for an investment of creative energy described by Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981), as 'psychic energy'.

of a shrine', as a photograph of the giver has been placed nearby.

EMOTIONS RECORDED IN SUBMISSIONS

Emotion is evident where it is expressed through the language used in written and audio recordings, the tone of voice in audio recordings, and the layout and compositions of the drawings.

Both written and recorded audio narratives use direct and sometimes overstated language and swearing (e.g. 'hate', 'crap') to express dislike, frustration, bewilderment or disappointment,¹⁰ and occasionally love or care. Submissions regularly convey the participants' frustrated sense of inability to use or dispose of the object as they wish. Within these submissions, negative terms such as 'can't' (11 cases) imply feelings of a lack of control.¹¹

The narratives that accompany the objects (told through audio, visual and textual means) are often told with lighthearted gentle humour, dry wit, or irony [figures 7 and 9]. In some cases this is part of the participant's enjoyment of and engagement with the confessional process of submission, but in some cases it is likely that laughter is a means of overcoming uncomfortable feelings, or memories of a difficult situation. There isn't scope within this paper for a full analysis of emotion present in voice and language but the author intends to pursue this possibility further as part of PhD study.

Emotions most frequently expressed through submissions encompass a range of feelings from frustration and disappointment, to mild regret, to love and affection. These emotions can be loosely grouped into the following categories:

1. Emotions directed at the self, such as discomfort or guilt at the participant's own lack of appreciation of gift (7), or participant's incomprehension at their own contradictory feelings about the object (2).

2. Feelings of frustration connected to the giver or the object, such as incomprehension, and recollected disappointment at receiving an object you can't identify with (12 cases, for example figures 1 and 4) or frustration with a useless or malfunctioning object. A small number of participants express mild regret at not having invoked the function of the object.

3. Affection, love, care or empathy for the giver. (4)

4. Expressions of empathy for the object, particularly in connection with figurative objects and toys that the participant can project an imagined personality on to.

5. Ambivalence expressed through not knowing where object is (2)

Figure 8.

Annotated drawing: 1970's telephone, in a box in the attic.

¹⁰ For example figure 7: 'It's minging but he's a legend and so will never throw it away'

¹¹ For example: 'so I can't bring myself to throw it away', or '...we kind of feel we can't do anything with, like we daren't even use them...'

EXPANSION OF FINDINGS THROUGH LITERATURE REVIEW

CONSTRUCTION OF SELF THROUGH POSSESSIONS AND HOME

Research on material culture in the home considers possessions as integral to constructing a sense of self (Belk 1988, Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton 1981, Marcoux (2001), Miller 2008). This research suggests we define ourselves by what we have, so it is perhaps not surprising that uncherished gifts, which we often feel misrepresent us in some way, embody conflicting emotions.

The need to experience control over possessions is reflected in the discomfort, present throughout the findings, attached to acquiring objects that don't adequately fit the recipient's sense of self.¹² Belk (1988) reviews research from psychology to explore the drive to physically control an object in order to fully incorporate it into self. He also refers to Satre's work to explain gift giving as a form of control, in the extension of the giver's self to encompass others. In receiving an object, the recipient relinquishes some control to accept the 'partial impositions of the giver's identity'.

Belk's discussion of Satre's theories of giving suggests a flexible self that can be shaped by the objects it extends to encompass. However, an intruding object could make an undesired impact. Research in human geography (Crewe et al 2007) refers to the 'capacities of certain objects to disrupt, destabilise and indeed threaten these self narratives'. It is also possible that a possession can not only impact on our own self perception, but can inform the way others perceive us. In his sociological work Goffman (1959) proposed that others interpret us through and in our immediate environment.

GIFT GIVING AND EXCHANGE, OBLIGATION AND RECIPROCATION

It is evident in the discomfort, guilt and mild regret mediated by some submissions, and in the implicit understanding evident in others that an object must be kept, that a gifted object embodies an obligation.

Mauss (1950) identified the obligation to reciprocate as a fundamental drive that is at the root of man's development as exchangers of goods and services. A gift given is always understood, on the surface, to be voluntary, but not reciprocating appropriately leaves a recipient vulnerable. Maus proposes that an obligation can be experienced through the object, describing it as an 'active object that prompts an action [...] leaves receiver in debt'. Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton (1981) develop Maus's assertion that giving a gift is giving a part of one's self, and is therefore a fundamental means of creating a strong bond between people.

The role of gift giving in nurturing relationships is present throughout the findings and has been explored, however there is not the capacity here for this to be included.

LOCATION OF OBJECT IN HOME

Literature that addresses the display and storage of possessions in the home provides a context for deeper analysis of the submissions. Recent research in packaging design and HCI relates both ephemeral objects (packaging) and emotionally resonant objects (heirlooms and mementos) to their physical location in the home.

Fisher and Shipton (2010) investigate the unplanned ways in which packaging is reused and the opportunities provided by the domestic environment for value to develop. They use the term 'twilight zones' to describe spaces such as garages, or cupboards under sinks, where an object can be stored out of sight, on the chance it will fulfil a later need. In research reflecting on identity and dispossession (Crewe et al 2007), peripheral domestic spaces are considered as 'liminal, transitional zones' where objects reside but are not quite thrown away. These definitions suggest a kind of physical manifestation of purgatory or limbo for objects not yet disposed of, who may yet have an opportunity to fulfill their potential.

¹² It can be identified in the following: In expressions of frustration at being unable to dispose of an object, in the frustration and incomprehension expressed in relation to receiving an object that misrepresents us, in conflicts over the value of an object between family members, in submissions of clothing that don't fit the recipient's projected identity, and in participants' strategies for preventing encounters with objects in purgatory.

In HCI Petrelli et al (2010) investigate the accessibility and visibility of mementos in public and personal domestic spaces, in relation to the meanings and memories they embody for the respondent. Odom et

al (2010) discuss the need for bequeathed objects embodying powerful emotional conflicts to be kept in 'deep storage' to prevent an encounter.

In light of the above theories it is interesting to consider the strategies participants have employed to display Objects in Purgatory in subtle and unobtrusive ways. Goffman (1959) discusses the performance of the self through 'front regions' (public spaces) and 'backstage' (private) spaces. A visible display of possessions could be interpreted as a 'frontstage' statement of attachment to the objects displayed. A private or backstage location could prevent an encounter of the object with either the person who possesses it, or an outsider (and therefore prevent a misreading of identity).

The development of the concept of habitus by Elias (1897–1990) and Bourdieu (1930–2002) provides a further means of considering the relationship of an object's environment to the way we acquire and keep possessions. The construction of the modern domestic environment supports and perpetuates certain rituals and modes of living. Some spaces in the home, such as mantelpieces, are constructed to accommodate displays of objects, and allow for (perhaps set up an expectation of) the acquisition of small decorative objects. Spaces built specifically to function as peripheral zones, such as loft spaces, enable us to accumulate without having to confront all of our possessions.

IMPLICATIONS FOR DESIGN

This paper aims to build on research in design seeking to prolong user-product attachment as a means of addressing over-consumption and consequent creation of waste. Packard (1963) first brought notions of product attachment to public attention in his discussions of 'psychological' obsolescence. More recently, the work of the Eternally Yours Foundation (van Hinte, 1997, Verbeek et al 1998) investigated product attachment as a means of addressing concerns over the volume of products that are discarded whilst still functional. Their calls for products that age gracefully, and for better developed services supporting the lifespan of products, have been further developed through more recent work on prolonging the physical and psychological lifespan of

products, such as Cooper (2010), Walker (2006) and Chapman (2005).

Further research in design explores emotional engagement as a means of improving the experience of products and encouraging interaction. (e.g. Desmet 2002, Jordan 2002, Norman 2004).

The discussions in this paper reveal tension and ambiguity embodied in possessions, rather than secure and uncomplicated emotional bonds between people and objects. That we can dislike something and yet still keep it, even value it, goes some way towards challenging notions of emotional attachment by suggesting that an emotional bond need not be based on desire, or related to material and aesthetic qualities. It is also apparent that we don't need to experience a strong emotional bond in order to keep an object.

This raises some pertinent points in relation to design. It suggests that notions of emotional attachment could be extended to encompass not only a deep 'love' bond or emotional tie but also the possibility of a kind of long-term tolerance. Peripheral domestic spaces can help support this. They provide opportunities for us to keep objects without confronting them, and for objects to develop value. This could be a consideration for the design of domestic interiors.

The above also presents us with the challenge of designing objects for complex social rituals that are subject to diverse influences. Engaging with these rituals, rather than focusing on the objects, could help facilitate attachment. For example, methods of open design or co-design could facilitate the personal investment of the giver, helping to create value in a product at the centre of a gift exchange.

CONCLUSION

The Objects in Purgatory live exhibition has much potential to be further developed as a means of gathering data. A second manifestation of the exhibition could further develop creative audience engagement techniques, as well as gather more basic data such as age and gender. The exhibition has social agency and is a valuable means of engaging an

audience in collective reflection on how and why we keep things.

This paper considers some of the complexity inherent in the formation of emotional attachment to a possession, and outlines the interplay between domestic space, rituals of exchange and obligation, and an individual's need to feel a secure sense of identity. Possessions are central to the construction of a sense of self, and an object intruding on this process can be troublesome. However these possessions can be kept and even valued, despite their disruptive presence. The structure of modern domestic spaces accommodates this, and the project also touches gently on a caring side to human nature, expressed as care for the giver or the object itself.

The above presents a challenge for design, because it undermines the possibilities of designing for emotional attachment through control of the physical and aesthetic properties of a product. In order to engage with the negotiated and evolving nature of product attachment, designers need to engage fully with the everyday social and domestic rituals that shape it.

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